

PEDAGOGICAL DIRECTIONS OF FORMING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, the main resource of the educational process is the communicative competence formed by students, and various approaches to the formation of communicative competence in students are analyzed. In addition, it is emphasized that communicative competence ensures adaptation of adolescent students to the life of society and interpersonal relations.*

Keywords: *student, pedagogical process, communicativeness, communicative knowledge, communicative culture, communicative ability, competence, communication, student, communicative methods.*

In modern didactics, the theoretical research of communication processes between students is gaining special importance. Most students today struggle to express themselves effectively. As a result, they are not active in the learning process. In the course of the lesson, students have difficulty communicating and expressing their thoughts. This situation is observed in all educational processes. Teachers struggle to fully understand students' thoughts. Because they do not have enough communicative competence to express their thoughts.

Based on the analysis of various approaches in the field of formation of communicative competence in adolescent students, we came to the conclusion that communication is the main factor that ensures the general development of the student. Communicative competences formed in students primarily ensure their success in educational activities. At the same time, communicative competence ensures adaptation of adolescent students to social life and interpersonal relations.

Communicative competence formed in students should be shown as the main resource of the educational process. This serves to ensure the future success of students. The more correctly the teacher chooses the methods of forming communicative competence in adolescent students, the more effectively the individual-oriented and developmental character of the educational process is ensured and the comprehensive development of students is achieved.

The formation and development of communicative competence among students is an urgent issue today, and the level of its formation has a significant impact on the effectiveness of the educational process. At the same time, they help to ensure the development and socialization of students. Scientific approaches and recommendations on the formation of students' communicative competence should be developed in accordance with national educational programs. State educational standards of general secondary education based on the competence approach require that the educational process and the teacher be able to guide the development of logically based speech and thinking activity of students.

The society of Uzbekistan is in need of active and active communicators. Each member of society should be able to actively communicate with others and material existence. For this, students are required to have highly developed communicative competence. Only then will they have the opportunity to actively communicate with those around them during any activity. For this, it is required to develop the level of professional activity of teachers aimed at forming

communicative competence in students. For this purpose, it is appropriate to envisage the development of specific recommendations. Teachers are required to be able to purposefully use methods, methods and technologies based on more communicative dialogue in lessons. It is advisable for teachers to rely on these recommendations in the pedagogical processes of lessons and extracurriculars.

Due to the purposeful activities of teachers aimed at developing communicative competence in students, the opportunity to use communicative, dialogue-based methods, methods and technologies will expand. As a result, certain achievements are achieved in the mastery levels of students. At the same time, the activity of students increases in the pedagogical processes of classes and extracurriculars. Most students develop a stable interest in academic subjects. As a result, they participate in classes with special interest, perform exercises of various complexity, work on creative assignments, and are able to independently compose projects, dialogues, monologues, communication texts. They start writing essays with special interest and aspiration. In these essays, they express their thoughts, thoughts, and views. They start working in pairs and groups. They work on algorithms with particular determination, explain their concepts and use different ways of thinking.

Effective formation of students' communicative competence also depends on the correct selection of teaching methods and tools. In order to achieve the goal of the educational process, the interaction and cooperation of the teacher and students is also important. A number of methods play an important role in the effective formation of communicative competence in adolescent students.

In the process of discussion, students' communicative competence develops rapidly. The important part of the discussion is that a particular problem is discussed by all members of the class community. the discussion method appears as a method that accelerates the educational and communication process that takes place in it. with the help of discussion, students of adolescent age absorb new information and help them to strengthen their point of view and understand problems from different points of view.

"Imitation games" are also of special importance in the formation of students' communicative competence. certain activities are simulated in training. Certain situations, events, historical processes can also be simulated. The scenario of simulated situations embodies the structural structure of simulated processes as well as reality.

"Operational games" also have their place in the formation of communicative competence in students. such games allow students to perform certain actions, work on the process and communicate with each other. For example, in the process of completing various tasks, writing essays, participating in educational events, students communicate with each other and with the educational material, work on texts, and demonstrate the technique of using words. These types of games are based on the simulation of objective reality.

In **"Role-based game situations"** students have a good opportunity to form communicative competence. In these games, they acquire behavioral tactics, perform certain actions, perform certain functions, and master the skills of occupying a certain position of a person. In order to organize game situations focused on role-playing, the teacher develops a "Situational Scene Model" and distributes the roles among the students. In this case, the content of the scene is strictly followed.

"Working theater" games are one of the effective methods of forming communicative competence in students. In "Working Theater" situations, students perform certain roles, perform certain behavioral actions, and establish effective communication with each other. In this situation, students activate their existing social experience, apply acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities, and manage to activate their communicative competence. One of the main functions of this method is to accustom teenage students to take a clear direction in different situations. In this process, they objectively evaluate their actions and behavior. They are able to correctly assess the opportunities of their classmates, teachers and other people around them to establish contact with them.

Systematic use of the **"Psychodrama and Sociodrama"** methods in the formation of communicative competence in adolescent students is considered appropriate. This process is very close to role-playing and is based on a theatrical plot. In addition, socio-psychological problems are discussed in "Psychodrama and Sociodrama", skills of feeling the situation are formed in the team. This is a component of communicative competence. Establishes a productive relationship with others, expands their opportunities to feel their experiences, feelings, and get into the situation of others.

Each method that we have considered above has its own didactic features. It is recommended to take these features into account during their use. In order to form and regularly develop communicative competence in adolescent students, it is necessary to use an integrative approach on a large scale. This requires the harmonization of teaching methods. Each method has its own capabilities and certain limitations. When using these methods in an appropriate way, it is possible to form a high level of empathy and communicativeness in students. The ability to enter into conflict situations allows self-expression and open speeches. In addition, students will be helped to demonstrate their reasoning skills.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2022-йил 28-февралдаги “2022-2026 йилларга мўлжалланган янги Ўзбекистоннинг тараққиёт стратегияси тўғрисида”ги ПФ-60-сонли фармони.
2. Давлетов Э.Ю. Ўқувчиларда узлуксиз таянч ҳаётий компетенцияларни шакллантириш // Узлуксиз таълим. – Тошкент, 2019. – №1. – Б.22–26. (13.00.00, №9)
3. Сафарова Р.Г. Инноватсион ёндашув асосида педагогика туркум фанларини оёқитиш жараёнида талабаларнинг креатив фикрлаш кўникмаларини ривожлантириш имкониятлари. Innovative Approaches in Teaching Pedagogical Sciences: Problems and Solutions, International Scientific and Practical Conference, 88-94. Google Scholar indexed. [https://kspi.uz/ Qo'qon 03.03.2023](https://kspi.uz/Qo'qon 03.03.2023)
4. Машарипова Н.Р. Ўқувчиларда танқидий фикрлашни шакллантиришнинг педагогик имкониятлари. Педагогика илмий-назарий ва методик журнал. - Тошкент. 01/2023 сон. 79-82 б
5. Машарипова Н.Р. Ўқувчиларда танқидий фикрлашни шакллантиришнинг педагогик механизмлари. Интернационал ссиентифис анд прастисал конференсе “Инновативе девелопмент ин тхе глобал ссиенсе”/ 2023, Бостон, УСА. П 95-97. [хтпс://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7111515](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7111515)
6. Педагогика энциклопедия. 1-жилд / тузувчилар: жамоа. – Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2015, 320-б.

7. Педагогика: энциклопедия. 2 – жилд./ тузувчилар: Жамоа.- Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” Давлат илмий нашриёти. 2015, 368 б.
8. Педагогика: энциклопедия. ИИИ жилд. Жамоа // Тошкент: «Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси» Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2017.
9. Петровская Л.А. Компетентность в общении: Социально-психологический тренинг. — М.: Изд-во МГУ, 2000.
10. Фатеев А.М. Современные информационные и коммуникационные технологии в образовании/ А.М.Фатеев. – М.: МГПУ, 2012.